

Reliance on courts and judicial means over strikes and negotiation in Politics

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Abstract

The twenty-first century has seen reliance on courts and judicial means rather than strikes and negotiations in addressing core predicaments, political controversies, and public policy questions. Courts have been at center stage in resolving labor disputes. One of the most notable judicial means of resolving Supreme Court cases was the Canadian Supreme Court ruling that collective bargaining was protected by the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms. Apart from this, striking is a social practice embedded deeply in the history of Canada. The Court is likely to consider the history of labor law to determine if the freedom of strike is also protected by the constitution. It is the possibility of a strike that enables workers to negotiate with employers in the present state of society as unions themselves are unable to secure terms of approximate equality. A compromised, suppressed, or limited trade union movement transforms into a capitalistic institution for disciplining workers and profit-making. This paper looks into why labor unions win court cases since 1982 in the face of the fact that freedom of association and the right to strike is enshrined in the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedom.

Keywords: Decision, Court, Supreme, Case, Labor, Strike

Introduction

Striking is a social practice deeply rooted in the history of Canada. Strikes are characterized by refusal to work and are typically political oppression or economic exploitation. Strikes rarely happen in Canada and are mostly used as the principal means of making freedom of association and collective bargaining effective. Strikes earn workers the opportunity to directly take part in processes that determine the working conditions and wages as well as roles governing their working lives, unlike other dispute resolution mechanisms. The late twentieth century and early twenty-first century have been marked by reliance on courts and judicial means rather than strikes and negotiations in addressing core predicaments, political controversies, and public policy questions. Courts have been at center stage in resolving labor disputes. One of the most notable judicial means of resolving Supreme Court cases was the Canadian Supreme Court ruling that collective bargaining was protected by the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms. In light of the Supreme Court decision, courts will return to the question of whether the Charter's protection of freedom of association extends to the freedom of strike¹. In regard to the question of whether collective bargaining is protected by freedom of association, The Court considered legal provenance, international law, and jurisprudence as well as Charter values. It is, therefore,

¹ Bok, Derek C. "Reflections on the distinctive character of American labor laws." *Harvard Law Review* (1971): 1394-1463.

possible that the right to strike will be invoked litigation parties to support or oppose the recognition of Charter protected right to strike.

Striking freedom has a long, complex, and legal pedigree in Canada with the earliest dating back to 1872 when striking was clearly not illegal, and thus there was freedom to strike. This though, does not shed light on the scope and form of freedom to strike. In the context of labor relations, freedom to strike is looked at from the perspective of freedom to associate and freedom to collectively bargain.

Question

Lack of adequate representation in decision making in Government today has cost teachers their collective bargaining agreement for better pay and better working conditions despite the fact that freedom to strike and freedom of association that lay foundation for collective bargaining are protected by the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedom. This paper aims to research into why labor movements lose court cases and how teachers end up being the biggest losers. The research question fronted for this research is;
Why has the Supreme Court ruled anti-labor way since 1982?

Research

Data collection was mostly secondary as it was done by searching through published data. The research utilized government publications of court cases, technical and trade journals that touch on labor court cases, a range of reports, public records as well as statistical and historical documents. The past data collected through the above means, together with online and offline searches were analyzed, reviewed, and interpreted. A systematic literature review was conducted. The review used scientific electronic library and the Google scholar to locate

scholarly publications between 2005 and 2015. Keywords such as Decision, Court, Supreme, Case, Labor, Strike were used to search the articles and publication on the subject matter.

The method of the searched was based on 19 publications relevant to the subject matter. The original works and reviews published between 2005 and 2015 were incorporated in the study since they were the most recent established inclusion criteria. Articles that did not fit in the inclusion criteria were removed together with those that dated earlier than the year 2005 and those that did not address the topic directly. New articles, websites and official reports recently published and done in the mentioned area were used and the data extracted from them used to update the data in the study. A great number of literatures came up on the topic in education and attitudes towards it, but were reduced sizably after analysis of the content of the articles to usable number. The following flow chart was utilized when selecting systematic reviews which considered that authors, publication years, study type, objectives and limitations based on the publications.

Findings

The findings show that many Supreme Court cases ruled in favor of labor movements in cases involving them. For instance, the Supreme Court ruled that teachers' right to strike is fundamental and is protected by the constitution. Following a ruling that stated that Canadian workers have the right to unionize to protect their interests, the Court gave teachers a bargaining advantage in any upcoming labor-related events.

In the periods of the 1982 Charter of rights and Freedoms, the Supreme Court set out many protection boundaries, including religion and speech. Instead, the Court narrowed its view to the Charter's freedom of association protection for workers, such as no collective bargaining

and striking rights. The Court has since reviewed these earlier stances and stated that the Government could only put minimal limits on these rights. The Court maintained that freedom of association protects the right to autonomy and dignity of vulnerable people. Dissenting judges sparked a backlash claiming that labor organization demands are insatiable, and the politics behind labor negotiations do not favor the Government as workers have a large control as opposed to the industrial revolution ages when workers were powerless.

The ruling overturned a Saskatchewan case in which public-sector unions challenged a provincial law that limited the right to strike by workers providing essential services. This law gave the Government a unilateral right to classify workers as essential and nonessential and used this to deny them access to effective alternatives for dispute resolution.

The history of the right to strike can be traced back to the 19th century England when strikers were subject to arrest and prosecution as criminal conspirators. Striking before 1892 in Canada was criminal for some trade unionists until 1892. The international human rights agreements backed Modern labor law that protected workers. Labor laws and rulings have been challenged by the Government, claiming that labor disruptions compromise the safety and security of citizens. Some of the notable strikes witnessed in Canada include the 1999 Nurses strike and the 2006 and 2007 correction officers, snowplow operators, and highway workers' strike.

In 1987, a liberal-minded chief justice Brian Dickson put down a formidable defense for labor rights citing Courts majority proclaiming the workers' right to strike and unionize. Since 1982, Canadian organized labor has lost ground owing to unsympathetic government policies and laws, economic changes, and globalization as the Government increases its hostility to unions. The Supreme Court Ruling recognized the fact that freedom of association has been eroded hostile governments and economic shifts.

The demand to be heard and incorporated in decision making that affects them is one of the biggest struggles of teachers unions. Worker participation schemes are seen in relation to the industrial relations within which they operate. Teachers' unions have, in the past, have either been apathetic or resisted participative schemes and have instead opted to conduct their relations and businesses through mechanisms for compulsory arbitration. Teacher participation in decision making at the organization level, rather than at the national level is still low despite the increased willingness to consult and the growth in the use of negotiated agreements². These have rendered participation practices uneven and not well-developed. This has been complemented by the lack of interest among trade unions and employers in increased participation for fear that the proposed changes might limit or restrict some of their existing powers.

The need for change is brought about by the virtual disappearance of managerial prerogatives, the spread, and growth of participative management and arrangements at the national and industry level, and such funds and superannuation funds which are managed by employers and teachers' unions, new legislations worldwide requiring consultative and participatory decision-making processes, the need to adjust to technological change that has resulted in tribunal orders requiring consultation, the search for improved productivity that requires bargaining at different levels and efforts aimed at transforming industrial relations and altering traditional industrial law for the achievement of fresh focus.

The need for unionism participation in decision-making gives teachers a chance to present their views to be reflected in the decisions made. This means that participative decision

² Josephs, Hilary K. "Labor Law in a socialist market economy: The case of China." *Colum. J. Transnat'l L.* 33 (1995): 559.

making needs to be strengthened and mutual trust in government institutions and encourage participation for the efficiency of an organization more flexible and to enable training of teachers where safety is maintained, where they are aware of the need to be flexible, where the competence of teachers is increased for the realization of activities aimed at improving their reliability and employability and where worker inclusion into future operations is encouraged and its competitiveness is increased³.

Teacher participation in decision making also needs to be encouraged for the purpose of informing and consultation about the state and possible employment development inside the sector. When the Government predicts that the employability of teachers in the educational sector becomes endangered, about possible future measures, especially relating to the training and development of the teachers' skills with which they would correct the negative development and its consequences and improve the employability and flexibility of teachers who would be affected by such negative developments⁴.

Participative decision-making has a range of benefits to the Government and the unionists including the fact that it encourages mutual trust, enhances a flexible working organization, increases awareness on the needs for flexibility, advocates for trainings for the purpose of

³ Weiler, Paul C. "The Slippery Slope of Judicial Intervention: The Supreme Court and Canadian Labour Relations 1950-1970." *Osgoode Hall LJ* 9 (1971): 1.

⁴ Brady, Kathleen A. "Religious Organizations and Mandatory Collective Bargaining Under Federal and State Labor Laws: Freedom From and Freedom For." *Vill. L. Rev.* 49 (2004): 77.

employability, strengthens of competitiveness of the sector, corrects the negative development and its consequences through training and development of skills; helps improve employability and flexibility of teachers and the reciprocity of material rights and obligations. Directly or indirectly, including workers in the decision-making processes helps prevent potential conflicts and serves as a tool for early resolution⁵. Transparency and legitimacy enhanced through early conflict resolution and decision making through employee representatives also help a business avoid a lot of business drawbacks that might affect its profitability at certain time points.

With the ushering in of a new industrial arena of enterprise development, workers are increasingly being appreciated and recognized as real assets, calling for their training and involvement in decision-making processes. This, in the wake of the ongoing management shift from Taylorist models to models in which workers' brains are valued and used. The decline of unions, apart from being viewed as a necessary step towards increased economic prosperity, also calls for participative management at company levels.

Participative decision making also holds a number of disadvantages such as lack of honesty and commitment on part of the management, social pressures to conform to group domination and dilemma that need foresight, such as actor involvement and formalism in place of freedom.

Conclusion

⁵ Fudge, Judy, and Eric Tucker. "The freedom to strike in Canada: A brief legal history." *Canadian Lab. & Emp. LJ* 15 (2009): 333.

Over the last decades, the world has witnessed profound power transfer from representative institutions to domestic and supranational judiciaries⁶. Due to this, Governments and organizations and unions do not have structures that see faster and mutually beneficial resolutions to standoffs. As an outcome of this trend, courts and tribunals are transforming into political decision-making loci. Through judicial means, labor unions, as well as teacher unions, have regained their voice and achieved their demands in Government and organizational decision making, improved pay, and better working conditions. Governments and other organizations have posed threats to the existence of unions as well as the achievement of their goals. In sum, trade unions and labor organizations have gained from human right agreement and laws that serve to protect their existence and workers' rights. The judiciary has, in this regard, been helpful to teacher and worker unions as they have achieved more for less time through judicial means.

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